

HC-130 Fuel Starvation Testing

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Abstract--On 22 Nov 1996, an HC-130P crew from Portland, OR, call sign King 56, declared an emergency stating they had engine problems. Approximately 3 minutes later, all four engines flamed out and the aircraft crashed into the Pacific Ocean. The resulting safety investigation centered around three areas: an electromechanical problem with the propeller synchrophaser, the fuel control system, or fuel system management. The US Air Force Safety Center enlisted the help of the 418 Flight Test Squadron at Edwards AFB to investigate different fuel management scenarios that hypothetically could lead to a four engine flameout. These scenarios were 1) auxiliary tank fuel boost pump failure, 2) auxiliary tank running dry, 3) fuselage tank boost pump failure, 4) fuselage tank running dry, 5) external tank boost pump failure, 6) external tank running dry, 7) improper priming of the crossfeed manifold (main tank boost pumps on and off) and 8) fuel gravity feed evaluation. All of these scenarios except for improper priming of the crossfeed manifold assumed that all four main tank boost pumps were off. If any of these points caused flameouts, proper engine recovery procedures would be verified during restart.

Test safety planning was paramount since the success criteria for each test point was one or more flamed out engines. The primary question to be answered was how many engines to affect for each test point. It was obvious that a build up approach would be used, starting with ground test, then progressing to one engine affected in flight. The decision was made to allow up to three engines to be affected if the crew had confidence in the ability to restart the engines quickly. The test condition of 22,000 feet pressure altitude and 200 KIAS allowed the crew

approximately 10 – 15 minutes to get flamed out engines restarted prior to a forced landing. If no flameouts were encountered at any of the test points, the scenarios would be flown with all four engines affected to prove that that none of these conditions would cause flameout.

Initial aircrew training was conducted in the HC-130 simulators at Kirtland AFB. Test procedures were accomplished just as they would be done on the flights. Emphasis was placed on engine shutdown/restart terminology and aircrew roles and responsibilities for the tests. In addition, all of the pilots practiced flameout approaches to Edwards AFB. Flameout approach procedures were developed during the simulator sessions, to include estimated altitudes required to safely glide to the field. These procedures and altitudes were later verified on a practice flight.

None of the test scenarios caused an engine flameout during the ground tests. The auxiliary tank running dry and improper priming scenarios did cause significant engine fluctuations however. Since there were no flameouts during ground test, one engine was intentionally flamed out by running a main fuel tank dry to determine if the engine could be damaged by a high power flameout.

The test flights were structured so that all of the flameout scenarios were tested on each flight. An increasing number of engines were affected as the flights progressed. The flight test results were somewhat surprising. The most likely scenario from ground test, auxiliary tank running dry, did not produce any significant engine response during the airborne testing. Both fuselage tank scenarios, and both external tank scenarios repeatedly caused flameouts. The

most likely culprit causing these responses was pressurized cabin air that could enter the fuel manifold through plumbing in the fuselage tanks. The first restarts for each of these scenarios were accomplished using flight manual procedures. Later, engine recoveries from both a fluctuating and flamed out condition were performed by placing the appropriate main tank boost pump on. This procedure worked for all conditions.

This test proved once again that a reliable aircraft with a good history can still have a few surprises. Changes are being made to the critical action procedures in the flight manuals of all USAF C-130s to reflect the results of this test. Simulator training is also being modified to cover this "new" emergency.

INTRODUCTION

On 22 Nov 1996, an HC-130P crew from Portland, OR, call sign King 56, declared an emergency stating they had engine problems. Approximately 3 minutes later, all four engines flamed out and the aircraft crashed into the Pacific Ocean. The resulting safety investigation centered around three areas: an electromechanical problem with the propeller synchrophaser, the fuel control system, or fuel system management. The US Air Force Safety Center enlisted the help of the 418 Flight Test Squadron (FLTS) at Edwards AFB to investigate fuel management scenarios that hypothetically could lead to a four engine flameout. These scenarios were 1) auxiliary tank fuel boost pump failure, 2) auxiliary tank running dry, 3) fuselage tank boost pump failure, 4) fuselage tank running dry, 5) external tank boost pump failure, 6) external tank running dry, 7) improper priming of the crossfeed manifold (main tank boost pumps on and off) and 8) fuel gravity feed evaluation. All of these scenarios except for improper priming of the crossfeed manifold assumed that all four main tank boost pumps were off, contrary to normal operating procedure. The objective of the test was to determine the Allison T56-A-15 turboprop engine response, as installed in the HC-130, to these scenarios which could introduce air into fuel lines and/or cause insufficient fuel flow to the engines at a typical cruise altitude and power setting.

Members of the 418 FLTS accomplished the flight test between 5 and 24 November 1997 at Edwards AFB, California, on a USAF HC-130H(N). Two days of ground test and four flight test sorties were completed during this period with the results showing that it was possible to flame out engines using certain fuel management scenarios. This paper will outline the results of this testing and the flight test lessons that were learned – or proven again. It will also show how an old reliable aircraft with a good history can still have a few surprises.

There are also a few lessons learned for flight test that were proven again in this program. The simulator training accomplished prior to test was invaluable in preparing the crew for the test procedures and for its intended aftermath – engine restart(s). Airborne practice for nonstandard procedures – in this case flameout approaches – were essential. The first try at flameout approach should not be when all four propellers are feathered. Finally, the most likely hypothesis may not be the correct answer. The auxiliary fuel tank was thought to be the most likely scenario after ground testing. It was thought to be one of the least likely after flight test.

TEST ARTICLE DESCRIPTION

The HC-130 model variant of the C-130, first flown in 1964, was an aircraft initially modified to conduct search and rescue missions, provide a communication and control platform, in-flight refuel helicopters, and carry supplemental fuel for extending range or air refueling. It was powered by four Allison T56-A-15 turboprop engines of 4,910 shaft horsepower each. It differed from other models of the C-130 in that two fuselage fuel tanks could be carried in the cargo compartment. The associated fuel plumbing for those tanks was a permanent part of the aircraft. The tanks, however, were mounted to the cargo floor in the area between the wheel wells and could be removed pending mission requirements.

The USAF HC-130 fleet has two variants, the 'P' and the 'N' models. The largest difference in the eyes of the flight test crew was that the 'N' model had an auxiliary power unit that could be started in the air to deliver AC electrical power. The 'P' model did not. AC power is required to start the engines in the C-130 and in the very vocal opinion of the flight test crew an extra source of power could only be good. The fuel plumbing between the two models was determined to be close enough to be a valid test for both platforms. It was therefore decided to use an HC-130(H)N, USAF serial number 90-2103.

The fuel system was a modified manifold-flow type, incorporating a fuel crossfeed system, a single point refueling and defueling system, a fuel dump system, and an air refueling system for in-flight transfer of fuel to receiver aircraft (Figure 1). The system provided fuel supply for the four engines and the auxiliary power unit. Each engine was supplied fuel either directly from the respective main fuel tank or through the crossfeed manifold system from any tank.

There were six fuel tanks located within the wing. The number one, two, three, and four main tanks were integral and used sealed wing structure for tank walls. Each outboard main tank had a usable capacity of 6,834 pounds. Each inboard main tank had a usable capacity of 7,322 pounds.

The left and right auxiliary fuel tanks were each comprised of units of three bladder-type cells. The three cells were interconnected to form one assembly and laced within the center wing section. Each auxiliary tank had a usable capacity of 5,598 pounds. The HC-130 fuel system incorporated two removable fuselage tanks, Benson tanks, in the cargo compartment. Each fuselage tank had a usable capacity of 11,016 pounds. The aircraft also had two external wing-mounted pylon tanks, each with a usable capacity of 8,358 pounds.

In addition to a direct flow capability from the main tanks to each engine (tank-to-engine), the system featured a twin manifold arrangement between the wing and external and fuselage tanks. The crossfeed manifold provided crossfeed capability for fuel transfer from any tank to any or all engines. The second manifold was primarily for refueling and dumping. The fuselage tanks were connected directly to the refueling and dump manifold. The two manifolds were separated by a solenoid operated valve, which was controlled by the crossfeed valve switch on the main fuel control panel in the cockpit. Each main tank had a submerged boost pump rated at 15 to 24 psi. Each auxiliary tank had a submerged boost pump rated at 28 to 40 psi. Each external tank and fuselage tank had two submerged boost pumps rated at 28 to 40 psi. The main tank boost pumps were designed to put out less pressure than the auxiliary, external, or fuselage tank boost pumps so that fuel flow through the crossfeed manifold would override main tank-to-engine fuel flow. The four main wing fuel tanks each had a second pump that was used only for fuel jettisoning.

A single point refueling receptacle was located on the right side of the aircraft just aft of the main landing gear pod. The receptacle was connected to all tanks through the refueling and dump manifold. A control panel was located above the receptacle to control fuel flow to the various tanks and to provide tank quantity indications. Due to the critical nature of this test, the instrumentation was designed with speed of installation in mind. The ultimate goal was to determine if a certain scenario would cause engine flameouts. Hard data for engine parameters were desired, but cockpit video of the engine instruments could give the required level of precision if required. Much of the engine data was extractable from the digital flight data recorder. Two important parameters, fuel pressure and turbine inlet temperature (TIT) were not monitored on the flight data recorder, and therefore were recorded separately. Fuel pressure transducers were placed in each engine inlet fuel line in the vicinity of the low-pressure light sensor. TIT was recorded from the temperature datum thermocouple in each engine. Because of this, the temperature datum amplifier was not connected to its corresponding thermocouple and no automatic engine overtemperature protection was available. This was not considered a limiting factor for the test. With a slightly increased vigilance the pilot could easily maintain the engines within normal temperatures. A cockpit mounted video camera recorded the engine instrument panel during testing. Audio also was recorded from the aircraft intercom system. A time code generator display was also installed and recorded to both video and data tapes.

Figure 1 HC-130 Fuel System

Several of the scenarios involved running fuel tanks dry. There was no way on a production aircraft in this configuration to transfer fuel directly into the auxiliary and external fuel tanks. To facilitate in-flight refueling of these tanks, a switch was installed in the cockpit to operate the left-hand auxiliary refill valve solenoid circuit breaker, thus allowing the fuel transfer. This enabled the flight crew to transfer fuel using procedures that were normally reserved for ground single point refueling.

PLANNING

With the safety of flight implications inherent with the results of this test, it was imperative that the test be completed with all possible speed. The C-130 Program Office tasked the 418 FLTS to perform this test on 15 September 1997 and requested a preliminary report of

results by 25 November 1997. The testing was to include 24 hours of ground testing and 24 hours of flight testing

The USAF Safety Center identified seven different fuel management scenarios that hypothetically could lead to a four engine flameout in the initial tasking. These scenarios were 1) auxiliary tank fuel boost pump failure, 2) auxiliary tank running dry, 3) fuselage tank boost pump failure, 4) fuselage tank running dry, 5) external tank boost pump failure, 6) external tank running dry, 7) improper priming of the crossfeed manifold (main tank boost pumps on and off). The Air Force Flight Test Center test team also identified the need to baseline the engine's ability to operate under fuel gravity feed from the main fuel tanks. This led to the last scenario, 8) fuel gravity feed evaluation. The objective of the test was to determine the Allison T56-A-15 turboprop engine response, as installed in the HC-130, to these scenarios which could introduce air into fuel lines and/or cause insufficient fuel flow to the engines at a typical cruise altitude and power setting.

There were concerns raised by maintenance personnel that flameouts at high power could produce engine damage, preventing an air start. Specifically, they were concerned about shock cooling on the turbine blades inducing stress fractures. The engine experts at the C-130 engine depot at Kelly AFB did not think this scenario was likely, but they could not completely rule out the possibility. Not wanting to leave anything to chance, it was decided to closely inspect the first engine that flamed out on the ground and in flight to determine if there were any visible damage to the turbine section. If none were seen after these events, it could be reasonably assumed that this would not be a limiting factor for the test. If the engine showed damage, it would seriously limit the test since it would not be desirable to restart an engine that could possibly come apart during the process. With the schedule concerns still looming, a spare engine was prepositioned at Edwards AFB to quickly change the engine in case of failure.

It was decided to execute the Fuselage Tank Dry, Fuselage Tank Pump Failed, Auxiliary Tank Dry, Auxiliary Tank Pump Fail, and the Improper Primed Crossfeed Manifold scenarios on the ground. The goal was to determine if any of these scenarios would happen regardless of flight conditions and to flameout one engine at high power for the turbine inspection. The ground tests were to begin with one engine affected by the specified fuel starvation scenario and then progress through four engines affected. There were two reasons for this build up during ground test. With the concern over possible engine damage, no one wished to go directly to the four engine test point and damage all four engines at once. The second reason was the thought that it might be possible to gain insight into engine reaction to the various scenarios. This insight would be valuable to the pilots during the flight test portion to identify impending flameout.

Aircrew training was considered essential prior to flight test. Simulators as well as aircraft were to be used to accomplish this. The simulator would be utilized to develop flameout approach procedures and emphasize crew coordination during critical phases of flight. After this was accomplished, the same flight crew would dry run the test procedures and practice possible emergencies that could be encountered. The flight crew was to remain the same for the duration of the test.

After aircrew training was complete, the flight test portion would begin. The approach for this phase was to run each scenario on each mission, starting with only one engine under test and adding another engine under test for each consecutive sortie. The one engine test points would all occur with the #1 engine. The two engine test points would affect the #1 and #4 engines. The three engine test points would affect #1, #2, and #4 engines. This lineup did not represent the optimum combination from an aircraft systems standpoint, but it more closely matched the order seen in the King 56 mishap. For safety considerations, two sources of electrical power and two sources of hydraulic pressure would be available at all times. The auxiliary power unit (APU) would be left running during all three engine testing

to serve as a backup electrical power supply. To take care of hydraulic pressure, the #3 engine would be left windmilling on all three engine test points if all of the affected engines flamed out. The #3 engine was considered the best alternative to keep the drag from the windmilling propeller as close to centerline of the aircraft as possible. It would not be feathered unless there were two good engines operating. The possibility was left open in the test plan to affect all four engines during test. However, this eventuality was reserved for the possibility that there had been no torque fluctuations during the one, two, or three engine tests for any scenario. We planned to perform the four engine test to prove these scenarios could not have caused the four engine flameout experienced by King 56.

A critical factor to the test team's success in meeting the demanding schedule was the priority given to this program at the AFFTC. The program had an AFFTC Priority 1, the highest priority available. This allowed the test team to receive the proper assets when needed. Although this was an accelerated test, none of the of the standard technical or safety planning steps were skipped. Each step was just completed in a much shorter time span.

TEST METHOD

The time spent planning paid big dividends when the test commenced. There was very little that occurred that was a surprise and therefore, very little of the plan had to be changed as the test was being executed. That did not mean that there were not unexpected results from the tests, just that most eventualities had been thought of and the outcome considered.

The aircrew training was absolutely invaluable. The test was of short enough duration that the same crew could be used for all events. Three pilots and three flight engineers were involved in all events so that there would be one extra crewmember if needed on short notice. The simulator was very helpful in fine tuning the test procedures in a benign environment. Terminology and procedures were practiced for engine shutdowns and restarts. It was considered especially important that all cockpit activity be well coordinated when the multiple engine test points were conducted. The precision with which the crew handled all of those points during the flight test was directly attributable to the simulator practice.

Flameout approaches were also practiced to Edwards AFB in the simulator. This was an area of concern since there are no flight manual procedures or performance data for a flameout approach. It was determined that the best configuration to start this approach was gear and flaps up, with the outboard engines feathered and the inboard propellers windmilling. The feathered propellers lowered the drag and helped the flameout glide to the field. The windmilling propellers preserved hydraulic pressure to the flight controls, flaps, and gear. The data available indicated that a windmilling propeller would maintain sufficient pressure through landing. Although the C-130 has a fully

reversible flight control system, the forces required to control the aircraft without the hydraulic boost was excessive and was not considered a landable configuration. The gear was lowered when landing was assured. Flaps were lowered only to shorten the aimpoint. The approach was a straight-in to runway 22. It was thought that if the approach was short then there were several different choices of lakebed runways prior to the hard surface runway.

Ground tests were conducted on a level engine-run pad at Edwards AFB, California, approximately 2,300 feet pressure altitude (PA), with engines set at 970 degrees C turbine inlet temperature (970 TIT), which produced approximately 15,000 inch-pounds (in-lbs) of torque and 1,900 pounds per hour (pph) of fuel flow per engine. Ground test was conducted according to the test plan, first beginning with one-engine fuel starvation scenarios and progressing through four-engine scenarios. Flight tests were conducted at 22,000 feet PA with engines set at 970 TIT during straight and level unaccelerated flight except for the left bank evaluation. A left bank evaluation was conducted at 22,000 feet PA with engines set at 910 TIT. Engines set at 970 TIT at 22,000 feet produced approximately 12,000 in-lbs of torque and 1,300 pph of fuel flow. Engines set at 910 TIT at 22,000 feet produced approximately 10,000 in-lbs of torque and 1,150 pph of fuel flow. Four-engine flight tests were not conducted because fuel starvation engine response was demonstrated during buildup and three-engine flight tests.

The aircraft was initially configured for each test point with all engines feeding from their respective main fuel tank. For all tests except improper priming with main tank boost pumps on, the main tank boost pumps were off for the engines being tested. Next, the test engine(s) were established on crossfeed from the appropriate fuel tank for the test point. All other engines were configured to be fed directly from the main tanks, crossfeed valve closed and boost pump on. The test points dealing with the auxiliary fuel tank utilized the left tank for all test points. The points dealing with the fuselage tank used the right tank and its #1 boost pump (standard operating procedure) for all test points. The manual isolation valves for both fuselage tanks were open in accordance with the standard operational configuration. The left fuselage tank had less than 2000 lbs of fuel for all points. When the specific test procedure for that point was accomplished, the engine response was recorded. The test point was allowed to continue for either a maximum of 10 minutes with no response, evidence of

gravity feed established as determined by the quantities in the main tank decreasing, or the occurrence of torque fluctuations/flameout.

Significant engine fluctuation was defined as a torque drop of 4000 in-lb) below steady state. Minor fluctuations were defined as those between 1000 and 4000 in-lbs. Fluctuations of less than 1000 in-lbs were considered part of normal engine operation and therefore were not significant. Flameout was defined as when rpm dropped below 94 percent. At 94 percent, the engine acceleration bleed valves opened in the compressor section and the engine rpm would drop to a windmilling speed (40-50% rpm). It was at this point the engine was feathered if called for. Following a build up approach, the first few test points in which positive results were obtained in flight were allowed to go no further than the fluctuating stage. After a successful recovery was observed, the one and two engine scenarios were allowed to proceed to flameout. The three engine cases were generally allowed to continue until torque had dropped to 4,000 in-lb on all three engines prior to recovery. In the progression of the test point, if the first two engines flamed out prior to the third engine reaching 4,000 in-lb of torque, the flamed out engines were feathered if an outboard and allowed to windmill if an inboard.

Engine inspections were conducted after the first engine flameout during ground test and the first engine flameout during flight test, as well as at the end of every day when an engine flameout had occurred. Engine flameout inspections were completed according to T.O. 1C-130B-2-4CL-4 and guidance from the San Antonio Air Logistics Center Propulsion Directorate. Engine inspections consisted of borescoping the turbines, low-pressure in-line fuel filter inspections, and high-pressure in-line fuel filter inspections. No damage that could be detected by borescope was ever seen in the turbine blades from flameouts. Also, no metal particles were detected in the fuel filters.

A summary of test results is included in Table 1. No fuel starvation scenarios tested produced engine flameout on the ground. The fuselage tank and external tank pump failure and tank running empty scenarios caused significant engine power loss and flameouts in flight. The left bank evaluation did not conclusively demonstrate a correlation of engine response with aircraft banking and maneuvering. The tested recovery procedure consistently recovered torque-fluctuating and flamed-out engines.

Table 1
HC-130H(N) S/N 90-2103 HC-130 FUEL STARVATION TEST RESULTS SUMMARY

Objective	Ground Test				Flight Test		
	Total Number of Engines Tested				Total Number of Engines Tested		
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3
1. Auxiliary Tank Pump Failure	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR
2. Auxiliary Tank Running Empty	fx	fx	fx	FX	NR	NR	NR
3. Fuselage Tank Pump Failure	NR	NR	NR	NR	FO	FO	FO
4. Fuselage Tank Running Empty	NR	NR	NR	NR	FO	FO	FO

5. External Tank Pump Failure					FO	FO	FO
6. External Tank Running Empty					FX	FO	FO
7. Improper Priming	NR	NR	FX	FX	fx	FX	NR
8. Improper Priming (Boost Pumps On)							NR
9. Gravity Feed Evaluation					NR		
10. Left Bank Evaluation							Not Conclusive
11. Recovery Procedure Evaluation					All Recovered ¹		

- Notes: 1. NR - No significant engine response
2. fx - Torque fluctuations of 1,000 to 4,000 in-lb
3. FX - Torque fluctuations greater than 4,000 in-lb
4. FO - Engine(s) flamed out
5. Blank cells are not applicable (not tested).

¹ All engines started recovery prior to the execution of the second step of the recovery procedure.

Auxiliary Tank Pump Failure

After the engine(s) under test were configured for left auxiliary tank crossfeed operation, the left auxiliary fuel pump was switched to OFF to simulate pump failure. In all situations, this scenario did not cause abnormal engine response. The fluctuations which did occur during this portion of the test were small enough to be within normal

engine and gauge fluctuation, especially during operation on the ground. The fact that no abnormal engine response occurred indicated that the engines smoothly transitioned from crossfeeding from the left auxiliary tank to gravity feeding from their main tank. Auxiliary tank pump failure test results are included in Table 2.

Table 2
HC-130H(N) S/N 90-2103 AUXILIARY TANK PUMP FAILURE RESULTS

Engine Response	Ground Test				Flight Test		
	Total Number of Engines Tested				Total Number of Engines Tested		
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3
Max Torque Fluctuations (in-lb)	200	200	200	300	0	0	200
Max TIT Fluctuations (deg C)	0	10	10	5	10	5	10
Max Fuel Flow Fluctuations (pph)	100	100	30	50	0	0	0
Min Engine Fuel Pump Inlet Pressure (psia)	13	13	13	13	5.5	5.5	5.5

- Notes: 1. psia - pounds per square inch absolute
2. Min - minimum
3. C - Centigrade
4. Max - maximum
5. pph - pounds per hour
6. TIT - turbine inlet temperature

Auxiliary Tank Empty

The aircraft was configured for left auxiliary tank crossfeed operation. The tank was then allowed to run empty. This scenario caused significant torque, TIT, and fuel flow fluctuations on the ground but not in flight. Engine

fluctuations observed during this scenario were greatest on the #2 engine and grew in magnitude as testing progressed in the number of engines during ground and flight test. Engines #1, #3, and #4 only experienced slight TIT fluctuations of less than 10 degrees, or no response at all. Auxiliary tank running empty test results are included in Table 3.

Table 3
HC-130H(N) S/N 90-2103 AUXILIARY TANK EMPTY RESULTS

Engine Response	Ground Test				Flight Test		
	Total Number of Engines Tested				Total Number of Engines Tested		
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3
Max Torque Fluctuations (in-lbs)	1,000	2,000	2,000	5,000	0	800	500
Max TIT Fluctuations (deg C)	10	50	100	100	5	50	20
Max Fuel Flow Fluctuations (pph)	100	150	400	400	20	50	50
Min Engine Fuel Pump Inlet Pressure (psia)	11.5	11	11	10.5	5.5	4.5	5

Notes: 1. Max - maximum
2. TIT - Turbine Inlet Temperature
3. pph - pounds per hour

4. Min - minimum
5. psia - pounds per square inch absolute

Engine fuel pump inlet pressure dropped below the ambient atmospheric pressure for each test point of this scenario. This occurred after the left auxiliary tank ran empty and approximately 20 seconds after torque, TIT, and fuel flow fluctuations began. The engines with the largest inlet pressure drop corresponded to the engine with the largest torque fluctuations. Fluctuations were greatest on engine #2, followed by engine #1, with almost no engine response on engines #3 and #4. The duration of engine #2 fluctuations lasted approximately 50 seconds during ground test and 30 seconds or less in flight.

Fuselage Tank Pump Failure

The aircraft was configured with the main tank boost pumps off and the engine(s) under test feeding from the right fuselage fuel tank with the #1 boost pump on. Once positive crossfeed operations had been established, the right fuselage tank #1 fuel pump was switched to OFF to simulate pump failure. Although no response was observed during ground test, this scenario caused engine flameouts in flight. Fuselage tank pump failure test results are included in Table 4. During three engine-flight tests of the fuselage tank pump failure scenario, engine #4 experienced torque, TIT, and fuel flow fluctuations, first followed by engines #1 and #2 within 30 seconds. Typical engine response from this scenario is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Engine #2 Response From Fuselage Tank Pump Failure (Three-Engine Flight Test)

TABLE 4
HC-130H(N) S/N 90-2103
FUSELAGE TANK PUMP FAILURE RESULTS (ISOLATION VALVE OPEN)

Engine Response	Ground Test				Flight Test		
	Total Number of Engines Tested				Total Number of Engines Tested		
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3 ¹
Max Torque Fluctuations (in-lb)	200	200	100	500	FO	FO	FO
Max TIT Fluctuations (deg C)	0	10	10	5	FO	FO	FO
Max Fuel Flow Fluctuations (pph)	30	30	20	0	FO	FO	FO
Min Engine Fuel Pump Inlet Pressure (psia)	13	13	13	13	8.5	7	8

- Notes: 1. Max - maximum
 2. TIT - turbine inlet temperature
 3. C - Centigrade
 4. Min - minimum
 5. psia - pounds per square inch absolute
 6. FO - engine(s) flamed out

¹ Test point plotted in Figure 2.

The fuselage tank pump failure flameouts were unexpected test results because pressurized cabin air was expected to force fuselage tank fuel into the fuel manifold to feed the engines. This obviously did not occur. The cause of the flameouts was thought to be cabin pressurized air entering either through the empty left fuselage tank or through the right fuselage tank's vent valve. These results are significant because there is a flight manual procedure, "Fuselage Tanks Using Cabin Pressurization", which employs a very similar setup to this test point. This procedure was meant to deliver an alternate means of providing fuselage tank fuel in the case of a dual boost pump failure.

In table 4, note the increased engine inlet pressure in flight (7 to 8 psia) compared to the 4 to 6 psia present during the auxiliary tank scenarios. The cabin differential pressure was approximately 7.4 psi. This pressurized air was travelling from the fuselage tanks to the engines of interest. The engine reverted to gravity feed during ground test of this scenario when the aircraft was not pressurized, but the engines did not establish gravity feed in flight. This supports the theory that cabin pressurized air caused engine flameouts by blocking main tank fuel

from gravity feeding. However, the mechanism by which pressurized cabin air enters the fuel lines has not been confirmed. This theory cannot be confirmed without further investigation.

Even without further investigation, the conclusion can be made that if a fuselage tank boost pump fails while crossfeeding engines with their main tank boost pumps off and no other boost pumps are providing pressure to the manifold, those engines are likely to flameout. Therefore, the caution contained in the "Fuselage Tanks Using Cabin Pressurization" flight manual pertaining to possible erratic engine operation should be upgraded to a warning.

Fuselage Tank Empty

The aircraft was configured with the main tank boost pumps off and the engine(s) under test feeding from the right fuselage fuel tank with the #1 boost pump on. The right fuselage fuel tank was allowed to run empty. Although no response was observed during ground test, this scenario caused engine flameouts in flight. Fuselage tank running empty test results are included in Table 5.

Table 5
HC-130H(N) S/N 90-2103
FUSELAGE TANK EMPTY RESULTS (ISOLATION VALVE OPEN)

Engine Response	Ground Test				Flight Test		
	Total Number of Engines Tested				Total Number of Engines Tested		
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3
Max Torque Fluctuations (in-lb)	1,000	200	200	200	FO	FO	FO
Max TIT Fluctuations (deg C)	0	5	5	5	FO	FO	FO
Max Fuel Flow Fluctuations (pph)	0	30	0	0	FO	FO	FO
Min Engine Fuel Pump Inlet Pressure (psia)	13	13	13	13	8.5	8.5	9.5

- Notes: 1. Max - maximum
 2. TIT - turbine inlet temperature
 3. C - Centigrade
 4. FO - engine(s) flamed out
 5. pph - pounds per hour
 6. psia - pounds per square inch absolute
 7. Min - minimum

During three-engine flight tests of the fuselage tank running empty scenario, engines #1, #2, and #4 experienced near simultaneous torque, TIT, and fuel flow fluctuations. Engine power loss and flameout occurred more quickly than in the fuselage tank pump failure scenarios, since a larger volume of air could enter fuel lines through an empty tank than through the tank vent valve line. The fuel pump inlet pressure once again indicated ambient cabin pressure entering the engines. If a fuselage tank runs empty while crossfeeding engines with their main tank boost pumps off and no other boost

pumps are providing pressure to the crossfeed manifold, those engines are likely to flameout.

External Tank Pump Failure

The aircraft was configured so the engines under test were established on crossfeed from an external fuel tank. The external fuel pump was then switched to OFF to simulate failure. This scenario caused engine flameouts in flight. External tank pump failure test results are included in Table 6.

Table 6
 HC-130H(N) S/N 90-2103
 EXTERNAL TANK PUMP FAILURE RESULTS

Engine Response	FLIGHT TEST		
	Total Number of Engines Tested		
	1	2	3 ¹
Max Torque Fluctuations (in-lb)	FO	FO	FO
Max TIT Fluctuations (deg C)	FO	FO	FO
Max Fuel Flow Fluctuations (pph)	FO	FO	FO
Min Engine Fuel Pump Inlet Pressure (psia)	6.5	5	5.5

- Notes: 1. Max - maximum
 2. TIT - turbine inlet temperature
 3. psia - pounds per square inch absolute
 4. pph - pounds per hour
 5. C - Centigrade

¹ Test point plotted in Figure 3.

During three-engine flight tests of the external tank pump failure scenario, engine #2 experienced significant torque, TIT, and fuel flow fluctuations approximately 2 minutes and 30 seconds before engines #4 and #1 followed. Typical engine response from this scenario is shown in Figure 3.

When feeding from the external tanks the crossfeed manifold was connected to the dump manifold through a one-way check valve. All fuselage tank manual isolation valves were in the normal open position which pressurized the dump manifold to cabin pressure. Therefore, when feeding from external tanks, pressurized cabin air could force its way to the engines through a one-way check valve if the pressure in the crossfeed manifold drops low enough.

This theory is supported by the fact that engine fuel pump inlet pressure slowly rose above atmospheric pressure as the engines experienced power loss leading to flameout (see Figure 3). This indicated cabin pressurized air was likely forcing its way into the crossfeed manifold, slowly blocking main tank fuel from gravity feeding, and flaming out engines. This theory cannot be confirmed without further investigation.

If an external tank boost pump fails while crossfeeding engines with their main tank boost pumps off and no other boost pumps are providing pressure to the crossfeed manifold, those engine are likely to flameout.

Figure 3

Engine #2 Response From External Tank Pump Failure (Three-Engine Flight Test)

External Tank Empty

The aircraft was configured so the engines under test were established on crossfeed from an external fuel tank. That

external fuel tank was then allowed to run dry. This scenario caused engine flameouts in flight. External tank running empty test results are included in Table 7.

Table 7
 HC-130H(N) S/N 90-2103
 EXTERNAL TANK EMPTY RESULTS

Engine Response	Flight Test		
	Total Number of Engines Tested		
	1	2	3
Max Torque Fluctuations (in-lb)	11,800	FO	FO
Max TIT Fluctuations (deg C)	610	FO	FO
Max Fuel Flow Fluctuations (pph)	1,180	FO	FO
Min Engine Fuel Pump Inlet Pressure (psia)	5.5	5.5	4.5

- Notes: 1. Max - maximum
 2. TIT - turbine inlet temperature
 3. psia - pounds per square inch absolute
 4. Min - minimum
 5. pph - pounds per hour
 6. C - Centigrade
 7. FO -Engine(s) flamed out

During three-engine flight tests of the external tank running empty scenario, engine #2 experienced significant torque, TIT, and fuel flow fluctuations approximately 1 minute and 30 seconds before engines #4 and #1 followed. It was suspected that the mechanism for air entering the fuel lines was the same as for the external tank pump failure scenario. This hypothesis once again could not be confirmed without further testing. If an external tank runs empty while crossfeeding engines with their main tank boost pumps off and no other boost pumps are providing pressure to the crossfeed manifold, those engines are likely to flameout.

Improper Priming

During ground test, fuel was drained back into the fuselage tank through the single point refueling (SPR) valve. This procedure drew air into the fuel lines through the #2 main tank. The SPR valve was then closed and the right fuselage tank boost pump was turned on to force the air to the engines.

During initial flight tests of the one- and two-engine scenarios, air was introduced into the fuel lines by using cabin pressure to force air through the empty left fuselage tank into the dump and crossfeed manifolds. The amount of air that was introduced into the fuel lines by these procedures was much greater than a leak could produce. Therefore, these results are unlikely to occur operationally.

A more realistic scenario was evaluated in three-engine flight tests. The three-engine flight test point used the same procedure to introduce air into the fuel lines. However, the aircraft was then configured to crossfeed from the left auxiliary tank, thereby purging the crossfeed manifold of air and leaving a smaller air mass in the fuel lines between the fuselage tanks and the right external crossfeed valve.

The aircraft was initially configured with all engines feeding from the main tanks. The fuel lines leading from the fuselage tank to the crossfeed manifold were then charged with air. The main tank boost pumps were off for the engines being tested. All other engines were configured to be fed directly from the main tanks, crossfeed valve closed and boost pump on. Next, the engines under test were switched over to feed from the right fuselage fuel tank without priming the crossfeed manifold. Engine response was observed and the test point was allowed to continue until after 10 minutes no response was noted or fuselage tank crossfeed was determined to have established by the quantity in the right fuselage tank decreasing or torque fluctuations or flameout occurred.

Improper priming scenarios caused severe but brief engine responses during ground and flight test. The more realistic procedure, which introduced air between the fuselage tanks and the right external crossfeed valve, did not produce any engine response during three-engine flight test. Improper priming test results are included in Table 8.

Table 8
 HC-130H(N) S/N 90-2103 IMPROPER PRIMING RESULTS

Engine Response	Ground Test				Flight Test		
	Total Number of Engines Tested				Total Number of Engines Tested		
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3 ¹
Max Torque Fluctuations (in-lb)	200	200	7,000	5,000	11,700	12,500	0
Max TIT Fluctuations (deg C)	0	5	170	170	470	570	0
Max Fuel Flow Fluctuations (pph)	0	0	700	600	600	1,300	0
Min Engine Fuel Pump Inlet Pressure (psia)	13	13	13	13	5.5	5.5	5.5

- Notes: 1. Max - maximum
 2. TIT - turbine inlet temperature
 3. psia - pounds per square inch absolute
 4. pph - pounds per hour
 5. C - Centigrade

3. psia - pounds per square inch absolute

6. Min -minimum

¹ Using the realistic procedure.

The procedure that introduced air into the crossfeed manifold caused large rapid engine power loss (to zero torque) during one- and two-engine flight tests. Engine fluctuations lasted less than 40 seconds as the engines recovered when pressurized fuel from the fuselage tank boost pump reached the engines. The improper priming with main tank boost pumps on scenario did not cause any engine response

Gravity Feed Evaluation

The aircraft was configured so that the #1 engine was feeding from the left auxiliary fuel tank. The #1 main tank boost pump was off. All other engines were configured to be fed directly from their respective main tank, crossfeed valve closed and boost pump on. Next, the #1 engine crossfeed valve was closed. Engine response was observed for 3 minutes and no noticeable engine response was observed. Each individual engine was increased to maximum power while gravity feeding. Gravity feed sustained maximum engine power at approximately 1,083 TIT, which produced approximately 15,000 in-lb torque and 1,500 pph fuel flow. The fact that no abnormal engine response occurred indicated that the engines smoothly transitioned from crossfeeding from the auxiliary tank to gravity feeding from their main tank.

Recovery Procedure Evaluation

The proposed recovery procedure, 1. Main tank boost pumps - "ON" (E), 2. Main tank crossfeed valves - "CLOSED" (E) was tested concurrently with all other test objectives. The recovery procedure was used for every torque fluctuating engine recovery, after the test point success criteria were complete, as part of the test point cleanup procedure. The recovery procedure was demonstrated on an inboard flamed-out engine windmilling at approximately 45 percent rpm, outboard flamed-out engine (less than 94 percent rpm), and multiple engines experiencing torque fluctuations below 4000 in-lb.

The engines recovered from torque fluctuating conditions within 5 seconds after their main tank boost pumps were turned on. When the procedure was conducted on flamed-out engines, engine start occurred more slowly. The longest time noted was 20 seconds between main tank boost pump on and engine #2 start when engine #2 was flamed out and rotating at approximately 45 percent rpm. Overall, 22 successful recoveries of torque fluctuating engines were accomplished in 22 attempts and 7 successful recoveries of flamed-out engines were accomplished in 7 attempts. The outboard flameout engine was recovered as rpm was passing 93 percent. No attempt was made to recover multiple engines with a single main tank boost pump; however, based on the rapid rate that the crossfeed manifold was pressurized and the

rapid recovery of the engines, this should also be possible. The quickest way to pressurize the crossfeed manifold is to turn all four main tank boost pumps on.

While not part of the recovery evaluation, it was noted that the unprimed fuel line scenarios on two-engine flight tests also demonstrated the same recovery mechanism when the fuselage tank boost pump was turned on. Fluctuating engines recovered when the pressurized fuel from the fuselage tank boost pump reached the engines. Torque fluctuating engines recovered within 5 seconds of fuselage tank boost pump on.

CONCLUSION

This test conclusively demonstrated that it is possible to experience multiple engine loss due to fuel starvation given the right (or wrong!) fuel panel setup. The test was designed to get the bottom line results in minimum time so many of the questions on the mechanisms of how these flameouts occur are not answered. While it would be nice to know the answers to the questions from an academic standpoint, the importance of determining the setup and recovery of these potentially deadly scenarios cannot be overlooked. There was evidence that hinted there was a problem with engine flameouts on HC-130 aircraft if the fuel panel was misconfigured. The overall purpose of this test was to determine if there were hazardous configurations, and if there were, what would recover the aircraft to a safe condition.

It is not a normal flight manual procedure to fly with the main tank boost pumps off. This test conclusively proved that performing such an act is an extremely bad idea. When feeding from the external or fuselage tanks, it was repeatedly shown that engine flameouts could occur when the main tank boost pumps are off and either the operating boost pump fails, or the tank runs dry. Testing with the auxiliary tanks was inconclusive, so flight in those configurations should also be avoided. It was demonstrated that turning on the main tank boost pump would recover an engine from one of these fuel starvation scenarios by restoring a positive flow of fuel to the engine.

LESSONS LEARNED

Simulator training prior to flight test is invaluable. The time spent in the simulator likely saved twice as much flight time by allowing the crewmembers to practice all of the critical procedures in a benign environment. For this test there were hours of boredom followed by a few minutes of very intense activity. The simulator allowed the crew to skip over the setup phase (hours of boredom) and concentrate upon engine flameout and recovery (minutes of intense activity). All of the terminology and procedures for the critical points

were practiced and refined so that when the actual event occurred in the aircraft, there were no mistakes.

Simulators still can't substitute for actual flight. The flameout approaches flown in the aircraft brought out issues that were not seen in the simulator. The most notable was the need to have extra airspeed when arresting the aircraft's sink rate to touchdown. The first flameout approach in the aircraft resulted in a go around when the pilot realized that tidbit of information at about 75 feet AGL.

REFERENCES

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BIOGRAPHY

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Sometimes the most unlikely test point turns out to be the best candidate. When transitioning from ground to flight test, the most likely scenario to produce engine flameouts was the auxiliary tank running dry. The fuselage tank pump failure was not given much of a chance because the boost pump is submerged. After this point generated positive results, a review of the plumbing revealed areas that would allow air to enter the fuel manifold.

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Photos are not available.